

Guidance Document

Version 1 (Aisling's version)

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Creating 'What about Open Science' was presented at the [UKSG 48th Annual Conference and Exhibition 2025](#) in Brighton, UK on 31 March –2 April 2025, and a further presentation for [UKSG OER Online Seminar on 7 May 2025](#), titled 'Games as OERs: putting the fun in fundamental discussions.'

'What about Open Science' in its current version was finalised after the unexpected death of Aisling Coyne, who was the lead creator on this game. Aisling was a creative, rebellious, curious, kind and intelligent individual with an amazing sense of humour. We hope that those who play the game, remix or repurpose the game do so with Aisling's rebellious and playful spirit in mind. She loved to challenge the status quo, fought for equity and was an amazing advocate for open science and open scholarship. She was also a brilliant What About Open Science gameshow host. Just the best. She is forever in our hearts and is terribly missed.

Abstract

This is a competitive Open Educational Resource (OER) game designed to create discussion around common open science concepts and ideas that everyone should understand but do not always fully grasp.

This game is suitable for all audiences with, or without previous understanding of open science, although participants with previous knowledge do have an advantage in discussions. Participants do not need to prepare for the game in advance. Participants will be grouped into teams where they first name their 'institution' (team name) and begin playing the game to win BOBs (Bogus Open Science Bucks) to spend on Open Science initiatives at the end. Throughout the rounds, teams will discuss Open Science topics (e.g. APCs). At the end of the rounds, the teams are presented with a 'Pricelist' and spend the BOBs they have won. The teams then explain their discussions and decisions.

Introduction

Welcome to What About Open Science? The game where Open Science wins!

This is a gameshow style educational workshop, where players work in teams with the ultimate game of winning BOBs (Bogus Open Science Bucks) for their fictional institutions.

Players guess letters to solve a word puzzle, spinning the wheel to earn BOBs (Bogus Open Science Bucks) for their fictional institution. Once the phrase is guessed, money making ends for that round and the discussion begins. The rounds repeat until players reach the end and are given a menu card and asked to spend their BOBs on Open Science practices. Players are not restricted by the menu - they are also encouraged to come up with their own ideas. The host will end the game by speaking to each team about their plans to spend their BOBs and announce the winner as Open Science! The game has been designed so that players will not only gain BOB's, but have fun, learn more about Open Science buzzwords through discussion, and make conscious decisions about how they can actively participate in Open Science, both now and in the future. Players are encouraged to ask questions, search unfamiliar terms, and discuss experiences. We hope that players will carry their ideas back to their real institutions and continue discussions there, enacting change armed with knowledge.

The current game topics are:

- Article Processing Charges (APCs)
- Ethics and Research Integrity
- Open Infrastructures
- Open Educational Resources (OERs)

Feel free to add your own topics in the format and consider publishing them to allow others to use! The downloadable pack contains svg files that can be edited.

We acknowledge as game designers that we have inherent biases from working in Open Science as librarians and research support. These biases may have made their way into the game materials.

The Purpose

The purpose of this game is to create a safe and fun environment where creative but hard discussions can be had about the buzzwords of Open Science. It is an opportunity to fill gaps in knowledge and explain things like the institutional services and support that can be offered, ongoing national projects that work to further Open Science practices and any taskforce/community of practice around Open Science.

The game has been deliberately developed to be as low-tech as possible, so as to not risk widening the digital divide and hoping to contribute to Sustainable Development Goals 4 (Quality Education) and 10 (Reduced Inequality). The game creators have included ideas for substitutions of game elements and encourage users to experiment and remix the game as it is an Open Educational Resource.

Chen CW (2025) argues that students can be better engaged in inquiry-based serious games with active thinking in playful settings without relying on digital items. In our experience of game creation, testing, and publishing, we have found that this game has great potential to elicit meaningful questions from participants which creates an opportunity for further connection to support staff, on-going or planned projects, and further training needs.

The game can be used by any audience, and we have experimented with PhD students to Board Level University staff thus far. We encourage users to tell us about their own experience with different cohorts, in particular if you remix this game for other educational settings than the University.

The game concept is readily adaptable to other topics in the space, for example, Research Data Management.

Remixes are asked to be published under the CC-BY-SA 4.0 license with attribution.

Aims and Objectives

The aim is to give the participants an understanding of the Open Science terminology and enable the participants to experience resourcing the area of Open Science with limited funding. Furthermore, the aim is to elicit discussions in the area.

The objective is to put the participants in a facilitated but self-led game environment whereby they define, discuss, and defend opinions on Open Science terminology and resourcing thereof. The objective is to empower the participants to knowledge-seeking and question Open Science practices through learning.

Learning Outcomes

Inspired by the Learning Types and Learning Activities by Clive Young and Natasa Perovic (2015), and the Summary Guidelines for Writing Learning Outcomes by Dr. Declan Kennedy, School of Education, University College Cork, we designed the game to hit multiple learning outcomes through the game activities. We used Bloom's Revised Taxonomy, illustrated below.

By Tidema - Own work, CC-BY 4.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=152872571>

Participant Learning Outcomes

(Given in reverse order, from the base of the pyramid)

At the end of the game, participants should be able to:

- Define the Open Science terms used (*Remember*)
- Identify the Open Science terms in use/practice (*Remember*)
- Associate the Open Science terms with their field (*Understand*)
- Discuss the Open Science terms (*Understand*)
- Dramatise resourcing Open Science (*Apply*)
- Assess the Open Science terms in practice (in field, institutionally, nationally) (*Apply*)
- Connect the Open Science terms to their practice (*Analyse*)
- Question the Open Science terms (*Analyse*)
- Argue for/against resourcing Open Science areas (*Evaluate*)
- Summarise the Open Science terms (*Evaluate*)
- Appraise and assess practices in Open Science discussed (*Evaluate*)
- Design funding for Open Science areas given on menu (*Create*)
- Conclude resourcing piece - justifying decisions in game (*Create*)

- Hosts should integrate internal support available into the game where possible.
- Sign-posting on a post-game hand-out is also encouraged.
- Mentioning National projects and movements in the area are suggested.

Participants will understand the definition and real-world application of the topics chosen. For example, participants will understand what an APC (Article Processing Charge) is, what it means in practice, controversial opinions surrounding APCs and funding models available to them. The opportunity for a host to cover internal and external support in post-game discussion is available and encouraged.

The Basics of the Game

Ideal numbers are 4 to a team, 5 teams maximum. 20 players' total. We have found that peak participant engagement maxes out at 4 to a team - once you go over this number, the most confident and/or extroverted voices are heard more than others.

Ideally 2 hosts - division of labour is up to you but can be done by one very flexible host. Two hosts are preferred so that a host is available in the room, while set up for the next section happens.

Game overview

The game consist of three phases:

1. Guessing the Open Science topic and winning BOBs (Bogus Open science Bucks)
 - a. We use Cruelty-free Hangman to guess the topic
2. Discussing the topic within each team/group
 - a. For this part, the slide deck is used
3. Spending the BOBs
 - a. Here the Menu card is used

Phase 1 and 2 are repeated - we recommend choosing two or three topics per workshop.

Checklist for game play

- Black/white board or flipchart (for scoring and recording team names)
- Flip chart for Cruelty-free Hangman (the phrase to guess is represented by a row of dashes representing for the letters of the phrase)
- Projector for slideshow
- Whiteboards for teams (1 per table) [Can substitute for paper and pens]
- Whiteboard markers [Can substitute for paper and pens]
- Information packs (1 per team)
- Menu cards (1 per team) - *we recommend laminating these so players can use whiteboard markers to circle items*
- Game Instruction cards (1 per team)
- Slideshow
- Wheel (3D printed, digital alternative or other, see below)

Ground rules

- Respect your fellow players. Opinions may vary. Knowledge levels may vary. We were all learners once.
- No shouting out the answers or a letter when it is not your turn.
- Your team can only guess on your turn.
- No writing on props unless directed to do so.
- You can look things up on your phone!
- Not happy with the money on offer? Neither are we! Fund Open Science!

Overview of files included in the pack

- Slideshow (PPT and ODP)
- Game files (PDF):
 - Cover pages for information packs for four topics (Article or Book Processing Charges; Open Infrastructures; Ethics and research integrity; OERs)
 - Information packs for four topics (Article or Book Processing Charges; Open Infrastructures; Ethics and research integrity; OERs) with In a nutshell and Action cards.
 - Menu card with an overview of what players can spend their BOBs (Bogus Open science Bucks) on.
 - One pager Game Instruction card
- Editable game files (SVG) - *to create remixes or new topics*
- Stickers (PDF)
- Read Me/Guidance (PDF - this document)
- Wheel link (URL)
- Remix posters (PDF)

The Wheel

We used the “Modular Prize Wheel” design to 3D Print a wheel for gameplay: [“Modular Prize Wheel”](#) by [Micron_Flash @Micron_Flash_218257, CC-BY 4.0](#)

This is not a requirement. You can substitute the 3D Printed wheel for:

- A makeshift wheel made with a spinner and paper ([an example from Youtube](#) which is unlicensed)
- A wheel from a board game.
- An online wheel creator ([an example is PickerWheel](#) but it is not openly licensed. Can be used without creating an account for free. Can also save and download wheels.) It is difficult to find an Openly licensed online wheel, although there are many results from a Google search, including a Google Tool.
- You could print numbers out and have participants draw from a hat.

What about Open Science currency

BOBs (Bogus Open Science Bucks) are an important part of the game, but can be difficult to obtain and understand as a currency. We don't understand the value either! When you create your wheel (or alternative), we recommend that you use values of 100, 200, 500 and 1,000 BOBs. As Host, you want the teams to win money, but not loads - we're not swimming in BOBs! To add a real life scenario in the game, mark one section of the wheel with 'budget cuts'. If a team lands on it when they spin the wheel, their money will be cut in half. Too bad, so sad.

If you feel like adding some extra tension and challenge, you could add two budget cut sections. Here is your chance to freestyle - do you want teams to win lots of BOBs to spend, or do you want to remind teams of the hard reality: Open Science is underfunded!

Game Set Up

Information Packs

To prepare for the game, you need to print several copies of each of the Information Packs, Menu cards and Game instructions. You need one copy of each for each group you are hosting. We recommend printing five copies of each.

Photo 1: Pack set-up, Munin Conference 2024 – Day 1. (Photo by Stephen Glass, 2024).

Room

This game works best in a room where you have tables and chairs set up in groups. You'll need at least one white board and a flip chart, and technical set up to be able to share slides. The host should also have a separate table to be used for the Information pack set up, as shown in the photo below. This set up, with Information packs by topic will help you organise each round of discussion, and is particularly helpful if you are hosting solo. Photo 2 shows ideal set up with the following:

1. Comfortable seating for teams
2. At least one black/whiteboard
3. One flipchart
4. A staging table for packs
5. A staging table for the physical wheel
6. A computer hooked up to a projector

Photo 2: Example set-up from Munin Conference 2024 – Day 1. (Photo by Stephen Glass, 2024).

The flip chart is used for Cruelty-free Hangman – Phrase guessing game (Phase 1 of the game) whereby the phrase is represented by dashes and participants guess one letter per turn. Teams can guess the phrase only on their turn, and win BOBs (Bogus Open science Bucks) each letter they get correct. The BOBs will be spent later in the game.

As no BOBs are awarded for guessing the phrase, guessing correctly is a more strategic move to prevent the other teams from earning more money. Once the phrase is guessed, the money-making process ends until the next round.

Photo 3: Aisling Coyne with the Cruelty-free hangman set-up, Munin Conference 2024 – Day 1. (Photo by Stephen Glass, 2024).

Photo 4: Sarah Coombs and Aisling Coyne with a slightly altered set-up, Munin Conference 2024 – Day 2. (Photo by Stephen Glass, 2024).

Group tables

Each group should have their own table and chairs, with a small whiteboard and markers (or paper and pen) available on the table. Each group also has the Game Instruction card on their table. No other items should be on their tables yet.

Host Tips and Tricks

(in no particular order)

- As the host, your primary role is to facilitate the game. We recommend two hosts working together. Host number one leads the group through the game including spinning and guessing, while host number 2 is responsible for calculating BOBs and filling the chosen letters. That said, you can absolutely do it with one flexible host.
- When you have a single host, the ideal numbers for this game are 4 to a team, with a maximum of 5 teams total. If you have more than one host, you may be able to have a few more teams participate but it is dependent on how you can facilitate the conversations. We have found 5 groups of 4 work best.
- There is no prior knowledge needed for this game. While the topics can be tricky, the sources available in the information packs will help. Participants can also use their phones to gain information if internet access is available.
- This game is adaptable to play fully online. We have included various options in this document. We do not recommend Hybrid as things become very complicated. We attempted a variation on the hybrid option and ended up throwing the online component out.
- All files are editable and open file types. They can be edited for your own personal situation. What Open Science issues are your institution wrestling with? Adapt this game to help tackle them.
- Audience mood is unpredictable and can range from sceptical to uninterested. This is a challenge with any discussion and can be helped by game-play buzz and host intervention.
- Remind players not to write on props unless told to do so.
- Pitfalls discussed below.
- Digital Replacements (wheel and hangman) provided.
- Photos of set-up are provided.
- Remember, this is a gameshow! Bring your best gameshow host alter ego – or if you don't feel adventurous; play it without creating a gameshow atmosphere.

The Unpredictable

There are many factors which you cannot control but may need to pivot around on the day. We encourage you to be confident in your hosting and remember that **everything will be okay!** Some examples of external factors and audience moods are given below.

External Factors beyond your control

Inevitably, something will go wrong. At every test of the game, we had external factors which worked against us. Knowing that they are a possibility allows you time to think about possible pivots. Possible external factors illustrated in the table below.

Audience distracted by work 			
One person dominates 			
Sound issues 			

Audience Mood

Audiences come in all shapes and sizes, and people have lives outside of work which may have an impact on how much bandwidth they have available to get involved in the spirit of the game. Encourage participation by engaging your hosting skills – maybe break the ice at a table that is very quiet or drop an interesting fact. **Be confident!**

Skeptical 			
Chaotic 			
Agreeable 			

Example Pivot

Sometimes, due to external factors, you will be forced to pivot. In the following example, Aisling was delivering What About Open Science in University College Cork as part of a 2-day Games event. The room requirements had been given in advance but when Aisling arrived, there were no flip-charts and the room itself was not ideal. Furthermore, due to 3D printing issues, Aisling was unable to bring a physical wheel for participants to spin, necessitating the use of the Digital replacement wheel.

EXAMPLE

- Digital Wheel on iPad
 - Handwritten scores and team names
 - Slides delivered as normal
- Flip-chart alternatives provided

Game Instructions

Make sure the room is set up before your participants enter the room. When the participants arrive, the host breaks the room into groups of approximately 4 people.

Game play

Setting the mood

The host will ask Teams to come up with Institution names for their group, as they are playing against each other to get funds (BOBs) for Open Science activities for their fictional institutions (Because we all know that institutions won't fund Open Science unless we find the money somewhere... like in a fake gameshow).

The host asks each team to announce their name and writes them onto the black/whiteboard for scoring.

The host will go through the first slides of the slideshow, containing information about the game play and the ground rules. Once everyone is ready to start, Phase 1 of the game will begin.

Phase 1: Winning BOBs

Estimated time (each round): 5-10 minutes

In this round, the wheel is used to win funds (BOBs) and the Cruelty-free Hang Man is used to guess a topic to be discussed in Phase 2. All topics are Open Science related.

The host decides what team goes first. This will rotate each round.

The first team spins the wheel for a monetary amount, and guesses a letter they think will be found in the phrase. If the letter appears in the phrase, they will win the amount of money decided by the wheel. The wheel must spin fully to count. This continues until the team picks a letter that doesn't appear. The host then systematically picks the next team to have a go at spinning the wheel and guessing phrases.

If you spin 500, you guess the letter E, and there are 3 e's in 'What About Open Science?', you get 1500 in your kitty.

The next team goes. They spin, guess, get BOBs and so on until a team can guess the phrase. Guessing the entire phrase can only be done when it is their turn. If a team lands on 'Cuts', that team's budget is cut in half...just like real life.

Sidenote: *If a team has no money when they land on cuts, nothing happens. Half of zero is still zero!*

Teams can only guess the phrase on their turn, and there are no extra winnings for guessing the phrase.

Sidenote: *Not winning extra funds for guessing the phrase leads each team to a strategic dilemma...do you spin and get as much money in your kitty as possible? or do you solve it quickly so the other teams can't guess? The choice is yours.*

Phase 2: Discussion

Estimated time (each round): 10 minutes

Once the phrase has been guessed, the Host will advance the slideshow to the corresponding topic slide with potentially provocative statements, and invite teams to discuss the statements and the topic.

Each team will be given an Information Pack, corresponding to the topic that has been guessed. This pack will provide basic information on what the topic is (In a Nutshell card) and a list of potential actions that can be taken in support of this topic (Actions card).

The In a Nutshell card is very basic information about the topic - the Host can add information to the pack based, for example information related to a specific working group or institution around this topic. The Host should also encourage groups to use their phones to look up topics if they want more information.

It is helpful if each group takes some notes about the discussions they are having around the topic, as at the end of the game, there will be a group discussion.

Phase 1 and 2 will be repeated several times before the Host moves the teams into the final phase.

Phase 3: Spending those BOBs!

Estimated time: 20-30 minutes

It's time for the teams to decide how to spend their hard-earned BOBs. What activities, resources and practices will each institution decide to fund?

The Host will give each team a Menu card. Using the menu card, which has suggested actions priced - teams will pick what their institution will spend the money they have in their kitty on. Have their decisions changed from the initial discussion? Has the reality of pricing ruined their ambitions? Have institutions decided to merge? Or, maybe the teams have other plans?

Sidenote: *The Menu cards should be laminated so that teams can easily circle items they want to spend their BOBs on. You can also print a blank Menu Card, and encourage teams to write their own suggestions, estimating how much BOBs they would need for their suggestions by putting it in the corresponding bracket.*

Once all group discussions have wrapped up, the Host will facilitate a final group discussion, where each group discusses their plan of action. To end the game, the Host will announce Open Science as the winner of the game.

Branding and colours

What about Open Science follows a colour scheme with shades of purple, green, black and white. The design identity of the game was developed by graphic designer Lene Sundsbø Falkhytten ([Stilongs AS](#)). Below is an overview of the colours and fonts used, which we ask that you follow if you are able to if you do a remix of the game.

Logo variations and variations of the *What about...* graphic are all included in the downloadable folder of svg files.

Font: Barlow / Barlow condensed.

This is an open source font, which can be downloaded for free.

#FFFFFF	#E6E6E6	#E0E0E0	#DBDBDB	#50E6BE	#00A082
#616161	#3C3C3C	#141414	#0F0F0F	#B496FF	#7850D7

Remixing Guide

This is a helpful tool that can be used when remixing *What About Open Science*.

Your Open Science topics <ul style="list-style-type: none">• File changes needed• Why these topics?• Signposting	
Training Goal What would success look like?	
Audience Who are they? <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Role-based group?• Knowledge level?• Requirement based?	
Learner benefits <ul style="list-style-type: none">• What will they know• Anything they take away? (sheets, links)• Learning Outcomes?	
Pre-requisites <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Location• Knowledge?	
Publishing Is your version unique enough to publish? Where will you publish?	

Please do let us know if you publish a remixed version of *What About Open Science* - we would love to see how the game continues to develop.

Example Remix Interactive Posters

Here are two examples of posters that have been remixed using the colours and branding of the game,

In this remix, participants are given post-its and asked to write down controversial statements they've heard about Open Science topics (for example, APCs). These statements can be used to remix the game, to create new topics, and to see what your participants' opinions are (in local contexts, at conferences, etc.).

You can ask participants to mark their opinion about an Open Science topic, for example APCs, and chart it on an emotion wheel - for example: [Gloria Willcox \(1982\) The Feeling Wheel](#).

You can then give participants the opportunity to write down their opinions on post-its and collate these for further analysis.

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“[Modular Prize Wheel](#)” by [Micron_Flash @Micron_Flash_218257](#), CC-BY 4.0

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